

water mainly comes from $Zr(OH)_4$ gel and dehydration-rehydration follows a direct relationship with ZrO_2 content. On the other hand, in the latter part of heat treatment, i.e. at 300° and above, the linear relationship reversed due to dehydration of $Al(OH)_3$ hydrogel.

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X-Ray Diffraction Studies on Coordination Polymer of Copper(II) with 2,5-Dihydroxy-*p*-benzoquinone

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THE study of coordination polymers started nearly four decades ago¹ and X-ray diffraction study of tris(1,2-diaminopropane)nickel(II) tungstate has been reported recently². We report here the

synthesis and X-ray diffraction study of coordination polymer of copper(II) with 2,5-dihydroxy-*p*-benzoquinone.

Experimental

2,5-Dihydroxy-*p*-benzoquinone was prepared by the reported method³ and its purity checked by tlc and m.p. An equimolar mixture of aqueous solutions of copper(II) acetate and the ligand was refluxed for 3-4 h on a water-bath. The resulting solid metal chelate polymer was washed with hot water, dried under reduced pressure for about 48 h and kept over P_2O_5 .

The elemental analyses were obtained from Microanalytical Laboratory, Calcutta. X-Ray powder diffraction data were recorded at Regional Research Laboratories (Hyderabad) on a Phillips diffractometer attached with a copper tube. The diffraction pattern was recorded at a chart speed of $2^\circ (2\theta)/\text{min}$ using the scale $2^\circ = 1 \text{ cm}$.

Results and Discussion

The elemental analyses of 2,5-dihydroxy-*p*-benzoquinone and the coordination polymer of copper(II) suggest the molecular formula to be $C_6H_4O_4$ and $C_6H_4O_4Cu$ respectively. The diffractograms of 2,5-dihydroxy-*p*-benzoquinone and the coordination polymer are presented in Figs. 1 and 2 respectively.

The diffractogram of 2,5-dihydroxy-*p*-benzoquinone consists of 17 reflections between 8° and $56^\circ (2\theta)$ with maxima reflection at $2\theta = 28.7^\circ$ which corresponds to $d = 3.14 \text{ \AA}$ (Table 1). The diffractogram of the coordination polymer of copper(II) records 11 reflections between 8° and $56^\circ (2\theta)$ with maxima at $2\theta = 17.2^\circ$ which corresponds to $d = 5.19 \text{ \AA}$ (Table 2).

Fig. 1. X-Ray diffractogram of 2,5-dihydroxy-*p*-benzoquinone.

NOTES

Fig. 2. X-Ray diffractogram of copper(II) polymer.

TABLE 1—X-RAY DATA OF 2,5 DIHYDROXY-1,4-BENZOQUINONE

Peak no.	<i>d</i> Å	<i>I</i> / <i>I</i> ₀ × 100	sin ² θ Found/ (Calcd.)	(<i>hkl</i>)
1	5.98	42	0.016 6	002
2	5.21	24	(0.164 0)	
3	4.63	72	0.021 8	012
4	3.59	25	(0.215 0)	
5	3.45	17	0.027 5	121
6	3.31	14	(0.282 0)	
7	3.14	90	0.045 8	030
8	3.015	21	(0.459 0)	
9	2.86	22	0.049 8	130
10	2.73	38	(0.496 0)	
11	2.60	16	0.054 1	131
12	2.458	32	(0.537 0)	
13	2.21	14	0.059 8	400
14	2.16	14	(0.592 0)	
15	2.09	13	0.065 3	231,004
16	2.017	48	(0.656 0)	
17	1.705	16	0.072 8	223
			(0.721 0)	
			0.079 3	420
			(0.796 0)	
			0.087 9	133
			(0.865 0)	
			0.098 1	042
			(0.980 0)	
			0.120 9	432
			(0.121 5)	
			0.126 7	234
			(0.127 0)	
			0.136 1	600,151
			(0.135 8)	
			0.145 8	251
			(0.147 6)	
			0.204 0	261,614
			(0.206 8)	

TABLE 2—X-RAY DATA OF COPPER(II) POLYMER WITH 2,5-DIHYDROXY-*p*-BENZOQUINONE

Peak no.	<i>d</i> Å	<i>I</i> / <i>I</i> ₀ × 100	sin ² θ Found/ (Calcd.)	(<i>hkl</i>)
1	8.26	23	0.008 7	100
2	5.9	18	(0.008 5)	
3	5.19	62	0.017 0	110
4	3.65	23	(0.017 0)	
5	3.18	31	0.022 4	111
6	2.9	22	(0.022 3)	
7	2.67	26	0.044 3	120
8	2.49	23	(0.042 5)	
9	2.296	25	0.058 9	103
10	1.99	19	(0.056 2)	
11	1.668	19	0.067 2	220
			(0.066 4)	
			0.083 0	004
			(0.083 8)	
			0.095 0	104
			(0.092 3)	
			0.112 5	320
			(0.110 5)	
			0.149 6	411
			(0.149 8)	
			0.213 2	500
			(0.212 5)	

The X-ray patterns have been indexed by trial and-error method, keeping in mind the characteristics of the various symmetry systems, till a good fit was obtained between the observed and the calculated sin² θ values. The unit cell parameters were calculated from the indexed data⁴.

The observed values of 2,5-dihydroxy-*p*-benzoquinone fit well in the orthorhombic system to give a unit cell with lattice constants, *a*=8.217 Å, *b*=6.935 Å and *c*=7.809 Å and cell volume=44.995 Å³.

This cell volume ($n=4$) gives the theoretical value of density equal to 2.089 g cm^{-3} . The experimental value of density of the compound has been found to be 2.1 g cm^{-3} , which is in good agreement within the limits of experimental error.

The observed $\sin^2 \theta$ values for the coordination polymer correspond to the tetragonal system to give a unit cell with $a=8.46 \text{ \AA}$, $c=10.298 \text{ \AA}$ and cell volume $=737.257 \text{ \AA}^3$. Substitution of this cell volume ($n=4$) gives the theoretical value of density equal to 1.814 g cm^{-3} . The experimental value of density of the polymer determined by flotation method has been found to be 1.799 g cm^{-3} , which is also in good agreement within the limits of the experimental error.

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Sun Light Initiated Changes in Aqueous Solution of Lysine under Heterogeneous Conditions

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THE effect of different forms of radiations, i.e. ultraviolet, visible and sunlight on amino acids has been extensively studied by several workers¹⁻³ with different viewpoints and they have

reported the formation of amino acids, peptides, sugars and other related organic compounds. Lysine, an essential dietary amino acid required for growth and maintenance of nitrogen equilibrium, is chiefly found in the plant kingdom as protein and in free state. The effect of ultraviolet light, a main constituent of sunlight, on alkaline solution of lysine was studied by Morokuma² and he reported the formation of several products, i.e. aspartic acid, glycine, norvaline, norleucine and cadaverine. However studies concerning the effect of sunlight on aqueous solution of lysine do not exist in literature. Hence it was considered of interest to study the effect of sunlight on aqueous solutions of lysine in the presence and/or absence of certain phosphorus and nitrogenous additives mainly used as fertilisers and results have been presented in this communication.

Experimental

Sterilised (30 min at 20 lbs steam-pressure) aqueous solution of chromatographically homogeneous L-lysine (0.1 g/100 ml; B.D.H./E.M.) was exposed to sunlight ($6500'$, $25 \pm 5^\circ$) for varying periods upto 40 h in transparent sterilised glass vessels plugged with surgical cotton-wool in the presence or absence of sensitisers. The exposure was carried out under perfectly aseptic conditions. Extra-pure inorganic additives were used. The exposed solutions were drawn out aseptically, concentrated in a rotatory vacuum evaporator, examined for any microbial contamination by usual techniques⁶ and analysed chromatographically using Whatman No. 1, silica gel G or cellulose layer (MN 30J) as stationary phase and n-butanol-acetic acid-water (4:1:1, 4:1:5, v/v) or butanol-acetic acid-pyridine-water (15:3:10:12, v/v) as solvent systems. The authentic amino acids were run concurrently alongside the unknown spots as reference standards. For locating and characterising the resulting products, ninhydrin, alloxan, isatin (all 0.1% prepared in acetone) and Folin's reagent (0.2% 1,2-naphthaquinone-4-sulphonate in 5% aqueous sodium carbonate) were used as chromogenic reagents⁷ (Table 1).

DNP derivatives of provisionally identified as well as of authentic samples of amino acids were prepared and characterised as described earlier⁸. Thus the photolytic products were characterised by their comparison with authentic DNP acids, R_f values, m.p. of DNP acids, coincidence chromatography and also by specific chemical and spectral methods⁹.

Results and Discussion

Aqueous solution of lysine on exposure to sunlight for 5 h afforded four chromatographically separable and ninhydrin-distinct products (II, III, IV and VI), but on irradiating the reaction mixture for 40 h, only two products (IV and VI) could be detected from the exposed solutions. The results